

Experimental Study Of The Wear Resistance Of A Coated Rotor In A Rotary Engine Using The Galvanic Plasma Method

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ABSTRACT-This study is focused to studying the possibility of using a galvanic plasma method of the piston head made of aluminum-silicon alloy. The coatings, which were applied in a water electrolytic bath, consist of alpha, gamma and mullite phase Al_2O_3 , showed very good wear resistance. The tribological properties of the different surfaces were evaluated using the method of (a fixed pin resting on a rotating disc) method. The composition of electrolytes with different current density and different current modes create differences in surface roughness, hardness, and thickness of the coating, which have a big effect on the wear of sliding surfaces. Scanning electron microscope images of the substrate did not detect any visible wear on the surface in the area of contact or coating layering. This study shows the importance of porosity, which promotes oil retention, which significantly affects the rate of wear of the coating. The results of the wear tests were used to estimate the wear resistance of different layers obtained by the galvanic plasma method (GPM) method, as well as to create a wear model. Rougher coatings may be desirable in low oil conditions because they have a lower friction coefficient. This can be explained by the fact that they have an oil-retaining structure with a wide variety of micro topography. The results showed the hardness of the formed layer at $22 A/dm^2$ was the highest and had the best wear resistance, while the layer formed at $30 A / dm^2$ had the highest thickness and the highest porosity among all samples.

Key words: *Galvanic-plasma method (GPM), wear resistance, heat-resistant coating, microscope (SEM), the tribological properties, reciprocating pin-on-disk, microhardness, porosity, phases.*

INTRODECTION

The development of new environmentally friendly technologies for the deposition of highly effective and reliable coatings for the protection and strengthening of metal products, undoubtedly, is today one of the most pressing problems of modern science and technology in connection with the increase in the seriousness of operating conditions, the aggressiveness of the applied technological media and the corresponding increased requirements for structural materials [1].

The technology of galvanic plasma oxidation is quite well developed to get unique properties, including wear and corrosion resistant, heat resistant, electrical isolating, various thicknesses and small porosity. GPM providing a unique set of physical, mechanical, and operational properties (in comparison

with current analogs, for example, anodizing), this method can give a different thicknesses of the coating required depends on the purpose and operating conditions.

Comparative tests of samples with GPM coating aluminum alloy and steel sample with a wear-resistant chromium layer were carried out. The specific load during testing was 90 N. GPM coatings showed less wear, especially at higher temperatures. The GPM method makes it possible to obtain coatings that are resistant in atmospheric conditions and in various corrosive environments, vapors, sea water, etc. Since the GPM coating is a ceramic of a complex composition, the corrosion resistance of the coating material is quite high. Corrosion protection of the base metal can be provided by the thickness of the coating and by controlling the number and structure of pores.

Based on the above, the goal of this study was formulated: to assess the possibility of applying GPM to the aluminum alloy AK12MMGH, to work out the modes and to study the structure and properties of the obtained coatings also to steady effect of thickness and porosity also the wear resistance. The adhesion of the coating to the metal turns out to be greater than the strength of the coating itself, and under load, there is no tearing of the coating along with the metal-coating interface. The adhesion values calculated from the results of Scratch testing reach 350 MPa. The average coating breakdown voltage is 600 V. The coating breakdown voltage with pore filling is up to 2500 V.

Based on the above, the goal of this study was formulated: to assess the possibility of applying GPM to the aluminum alloy AK12MMGH, Modification with the help of GPM makes it possible to increase the resource and reliability of parts of the Internal Combustion Engine (ICE), also protect them from high-temperature gas erosion and reduce the temperature of the base metal by 1.5 times [7-12]. To work out the modes and to study the structure and properties of the obtained coatings.

Materials and Research Methods

The pulse shape (mode) and the processing time during which the layer will be formed are selected. The shape of the pulse is determined by the opening and closing times of the corresponding thyristors, as a result of which the energy accumulated in the capacitors is discharged at arbitrary intervals. To study the characteristics of the coatings, 6 samples of the AK4 alloy were taken. To start research on the value of the sample area, it was necessary to calculate the capacitance of the capacitors for each sample based on the specific capacitance that provides the required average process current. From the experience of forming coatings on AK4 alloys, the specific capacity was used for each sample. Examples of calculating capacity are given in Table 1.

The main parameters of the	Unit. measurements	Condenser (strictly)	Capacitor regulation control	Anode-cathode mode (17 Hz)	Anode-cathode mode (50 Hz)
Set capacity C1set	UF		13	11	10
Set capacity C2set	UF	12	13	11	10
VS1 ON	deg.		0	450	90
VS1OFF	deg.		360	630	360
VS2ON	deg.		0	0	0
VS2OFF	deg.		90	90	90
VS3ON	deg.		180	540	180
VS3OFF	deg.		270	630	270
VS4ON	deg.		0	990	0
VS4OFF	deg.		360	90	360
Rated current I	A	0.63	0.70	0.60	0.54
Frequency	Hz	50	50	17	50
Processing time	sec	1800	1800	1800	1800

Table 1 Specified parameters for current mode

After the parameters were set, the GPM process was launched. To start the process.

To continue the research, 5 samples were taken, the electrolyte Na₂SiO₃ (20 g / L) KOH (6 g / L) and distilled water (3 L) were prepared, and the electrolyte Na₂SiO₃ (20 g / L) was prepared for processing samples 4, 5, 6

KOH (6 g / L) distilled water (3 L) ZrO (OH) 2 (0.5 g / L), and the MAO condenser mode is selected, since only in this mode the oxide film grows to form a layer. After the preparation of the MAO installation and the setting of the corresponding parameters, such as: capacitor capacity, frequency and processing time, the MAO process was carried out. The process data were recorded at the end of the time allotted for each sample.

Results and discussion

According to the X-ray phase analysis data, the phase composition of the alloy is represented by a solid solution based on aluminum and a secondary phase Al₇Si, which is uniformly distributed over the volume of the material. The average particle size of Al₇Si is $2.4 \pm 0.2\mu\text{m}$.

In fig. 1 the distribution of total and working coatings thicknesses depending on the GPM mode is shown in and also shows cross-sections of coated samples obtained by the GPM method under various conditions. As can be seen from the above images, several layers can be distinguished in the structure of the coatings, the formation of which is typical for the case of using the GPM method on aluminum alloys [6, 7].

In fig. 2 using the example of sample No. 3, the lines indicate the boundaries of the layers:

1. Thin transition layer ~ 3-5 μm ;
2. Working layer ~ 70-120 μm ;
3. Technological layer ~ 30 μm .

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the upper unconsolidated technological layer typical for all studied samples is shown in (Fig. 3). The amorphous halo indicates that the main component of this layer is the X-ray amorphous phase.

When the engine is operating in the combustion chamber, the temperature is 1250-1450 ° C, as a result of which the metastable γ and δ phase undergoes irreversible polymorphic transformation into α -Al₂O₃, this phase has low thermal conductivity, and in combination with the porous one serves as a thermal barrier.

The energy dispersive microanalysis data (Fig. 3) correlate with the XRD data. In particular, an increase in oxygen concentration can be seen when going from alloy to coating. Also,

Figure 1. Coatings by the method of GPM on the AlSi12Cu alloy: a- No. 1; b - No. 2; c –№3; d - No. 4; e - No. 5 (cross-section).

as the distance from the substrate increases, the concentration of elements contained in the electrolyte, for example, potassium, increases.

As can be seen, in the locations of the silicon-containing phase Al_7Si , the highest porosity of the coating is observed, especially in the region of the transition layer of sample 1 (Fig. 1, c) is shown. Thus, the amount of silicon in the alloy - 13%, leads to the formation of a coating with a low density and a low coefficient of thermal conductivity [11].

As can be seen from Fig. 2, coating sample No. 5 has the smallest thickness. An increase in the capacitance of the capacitor of the installation during oxidation in identical electrolytes promotes an increase in the thickness of the formed coating. This is due to an increase in the energy of microarc discharges, which facilitate the penetration of discharges to a greater depth. It can also be noted that the use of an electrolyte with a composition of 9 g / L KOH + 10 g / L Na_2SiO_3 leads to the growth of a

coating on the surface of the aluminum alloy, which has the lowest porosity among the studied states, both in the transition layer and in the working layer.

If we compare samples No. 2 and No. 5, we can conclude that a simultaneous decrease in the content of KOH and an increase in the content of Sodium silicate in the electrolyte makes it possible to obtain the most porous coating characterized by large average pore size. An increase in the thickness of the formed coating is also observed. According to the literature [8, 9, 10], the developed volumetric porosity should contribute to a significant decrease in the heat capacity and thermal conductivity of the coating, which is expected to have a favorable effect on its heat barrier properties and reduce the level of thermal cycling effect on the base aluminum alloy, samples 4 and 5.

Figure 2. The layered structure of the coating on the example of sample No. 3, obtained by the GPM method [7]: 1-transition layer; 2- working layer; 3- technological layer.

Figure 3. X-ray diffraction patterns of the working layer of deposited coatings of various processing modes

Figure 4. Distribution of microhardness over the coating thickness over all sample.

From Fig. 4, we can see that the sample NO.5 coating was the highest in microhardness. The reason for this is related to the phase transformation in the GPM process and the micro porosity of the coating

and big Working layer compare with others. But sample NO.5 It was the least in microhardness although it is contained a big Working layer but, it has the maximum porosity of the coating (~ 1.99%)

Fig. 5 shows the wear losses surface of coating for all sample under the load of 90 N tests were done on a reciprocating pin-on-disk tribometer made in our lab. all of the samples have a different wear rate as shown in table 2, can be noticed the maximum wear rate was in sample No 4 near to $1.6183E-06$ (mm^3/Nm) but minimum wear losses was in sample No 5 equal to $10 \mu\text{m}$ only, The surface of the GPM coating is too rough to measure the amount of wear, so the surface is ground and then subjected to a wear test.

Figure 5. The wear losses surface of coating for all sample under the load of 90 N

It was also found that the roughness value of the coating of this sample No. 5 increased with increasing current density. Bulk oxide coating forms at higher current density levels; In addition, small pores are also responsible for increased surface roughness (see Fig. 6).

a)

ISO 4287			
Amplitude parameters - Roughness profile			
Rp	21	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rv	20.6	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rz	41.6	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rc	21.5	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rt	56.4	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Ra	7.48	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rq	9.3	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rsk	0.136	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rku	3.17	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Material Ratio parameters - Roughness profile			
Rmr	0.1	%	c = 1 µm under the highest peak, Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rdc	15.3	µm	a = 20%, q = 80%, Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm

b)

ISO 4287			
Amplitude parameters - Roughness profile			
Rp	6.56	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rv	16.2	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rz	22.8	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rc	8.63	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rt	30.4	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Ra	3.47	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rq	4.62	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rsk	-1.58	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rku	5.9	µm	Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Material Ratio parameters - Roughness profile			
Rmr	0.2	%	c = 1 µm under the highest peak, Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm
Rdc	6.37	µm	a = 20%, q = 80%, Gaussian filter, 0.8 mm

c)

Figure 6. Roughness surface parameters a) depth of hole of wear track, b) roughness average R_a (μm) before wear tracking, c) roughness average R_a (μm) at wear tracking

Conclusions

Ceramic coatings formed by the electroplating method show excellent wear resistance in dry sliding conditions on a cast iron pin. The surface wear rate of the coated material is three orders of magnitude lower than that of the uncoated alloy substrate.

It was found that the wear rate of the coating varies with thickness within the working layer and decreases from the surface to the metal substrate-coating interface. In the process of prolonged friction and wear, the canter-body material is embedded in the pores of the coating, leading to the appearance of a lubrication effect, which reduces the coefficient of friction and wear of the coating.

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